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Enunciation of Tacit Resistance in Nicole Dennis Benn’s *Here Comes the Sun*

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Abstract:

The study entitled “Enunciation of Tacit Resistance in Nicole Dennis-Benn’s *Here Comes the Sun*” focuses on how women use their bodies as a ground to opine their identity as well as to resist the power of domination. The objectification and commodification of the female body have been there in the history of mankind from time immemorial. But how they use the same body as a weapon against the oppression, as well as to survive in a society which upholds stereotypical notions, is purely intriguing. The nuances of response to the societal expectations in turn affect the identity and even the destiny of women. Women’s bodies are often subjected to societal standards, and failing to meet such expectations makes them inadequate. In order to meet the beauty standards and prove their compatibility, women find ways that could destroy them physically and emotionally as well. The paper delves deeper into the lives of marginalised women, especially of colour and the challenges they face due to tourism, economic disparity, colourism, social construct, and the cycle of generational trauma. Hegemonising and thereby normalising the societal norms instilled in the marginalised,

particularly women, forces them to choose paths to survive, which transforms into a subtle art of resistance and resilience.

Keywords: Body politics, power domination, stereotype, marginalised, female body, generational trauma.

Body politics is the system of hegemonising bodies in the context of the power hierarchy and the norms that exist in the society. It is an umbrella concept that embraces various disciplines such as anthropology, sociology, political science, philosophy, and gender studies. Going back to history, the female body has always been objectified and stereotyped as a commodity. As a part of resistance and survival, women use the same body as a weapon against societal standards. Resilience as well as resistance play their role in this context accordingly. Michel Foucault, the pioneer of body politics, examined how social institutions exercised their power over the body, while Susan Bordo, an American philosopher, analysed the cultural milieu and representations of the body through media and fiction, particularly among women. When society expects so-called beauty in the female body, they are forced to find ways to be accepted and treated equally despite class and race. Nevertheless, Judith Butler stated her view on body politics with the concept of gender performativity, which establishes the idea that gender is performatively constructed.

Women's bodies are often subjected to societal standards, and failing to meet such expectations makes them dismissed as inadequate. Body bleaching or skin lightening is such a complex affair pertaining to this scenario, which reflects the comprehensive societal pressures associated with gender and race. The body acts as a ground for the asseveration of identity, which includes a person's gender, race and sexuality. While society tries to dominate the female body, body politics tries to explore how dejected groups make use of this same body to opine their identity as well as to resist the power of domination. Movements such as Black Lives

Matter, M4BL, Say Her Name et al articulate how body politics resists oppression. Jade Thirlwall (@jadethirlwall) posted a song in Instagram named Black Breath, where she captioned it with thought-provoking statement related to Black Lives Matter: “You can’t play ignorance, justified by feeling comfortable, when Black people have been made to feel uncomfortable their entire lives in a white privileged, systematically racist and unfair society that is more than happy to benefit from Black culture” (Thirlwall, I’ve chosen to post” sentence 16, *Instagram*, 1 June, 2020). Though reproductive rights and transgender rights are also ingredients in this boiling cauldron of body politics, this paper aims to focus on how societal expectations of beauty standards impact the lives and dreams of women, along with their struggle for survival, which is beautifully portrayed in “*Here Comes the Sun*, a Jamaican novel penned by Nicole Dennis-Benn.

Nicole Dennis-Benn has been widely acknowledged not only for her literary contributions but also for the representation of Caribbean and LGBTQ+ voices. Being a woman of colour with a queer identity, she has depicted her own personal struggles through her characters. And this gives the reader a much more authentic picturisation of underprivileged communities, particularly women. Though she moved to the United States for higher education, her roots in Jamaica helped her to authentically articulate the experience of Black women strangled under societal norms and expectations. Her debut novel, *Here Comes the Sun*, which was published in 2016, received critical acclaim as it explored the themes of identity, tourism, sexuality, and economic exploitation, respectively. By delving deep into the lives of her characters, Dennis-Benn tried to portray the unvoiced screams of Jamaican women, and the paths they chose to wrestle with the destiny that was thrust upon them.

Here Comes the Sun, a 2016 novel set in Montego Bay, Jamaica, explores the lives of marginalised women and the challenges they faced due to tourism, economic disparity, social

constructs, and generational trauma. On a ground level, apart from the humanitarian values and emotions, the novel also talks about the deterioration of the environment caused by the excessive impact of tourism and development. The lives of native islanders who are marginalised are at stake due to the external domination posed by those in power. The ways they adapt to survive in the adverse scenario involve sacrificing their identity and selves. *Here Comes the Sun* showcases different methods of struggle as well as different forms of response to these challenges, where people relinquish their dreams and desires in order to survive. Though Margot, Thandi and Delores are the major characters representing the miseries of three different phases of female persona, there are several other characters that help to explain the distress of the community through their lived experiences. Generational trauma is yet another cause that makes the already worsening scene much more miserable. The transmission of traumatic experience resulting from the legacy of slavery, racism, segregation and the like can create psychological effects from one generation to the next. It can have long-lasting impacts on individuals, which can alter their entire way of life. The bodies of these female characters are commodified, objectified, and assaulted by society and its venomous components, starting from their ancestors.

Here Comes the Sun is intricately developed, portraying each character with a rich tapestry of human emotions and their experiences. The journeys they underwent are renditions of a wider social scenario, which provides the readers with a veritable side of the Jamaican community. Margot is one of the three major female characters whose ambition and determination made her take a less chosen path than others. On her journey to get a safe future for her younger sister Thandi, Margot sacrifices her passion and her body. Her body becomes a commodity she uses to achieve anything she desires, be it power or luxury. Her transactional sex with wealthy tourists and the hotel's owner, Alphonso, convinced her about how far her body can help her climb the social ladder. Generations of trauma that were passed on to Margot

made her take a decision to safeguard Thandi from the same fate that has engulfed her. Margot's strained and complex relationship with her mother forced her to treat her body as her own, sacrificing it especially for the sake of others: "Thandi, whom she clothed, sheltered, fed, gave every bit of herself to. With her body, she shielded her sister from Delores's wrath. Give her an opportunity to get away. To be better than them so she wouldn't have to sacrifice anything" (271).

Survival is the fundamental thing they can do in these adverse conditions. Each characters find different survival techniques to cope with their surrounding environment. Dolores, mother of Margot and Thandi, is in constant pursuit of survival by manipulating her elder daughter to attain financial stability and thereby start a better life. Though her harsh nature stems from a life of hardships, her behaviour towards Margot is totally unacceptable. Margot is denied the motherly love and affection she craves. In spite of the fact that she is aware of her coloured body and how it looked, Thandi's painting of Delores looking in the mirror crashed her with shock seeing her daughter's perception of her: "In this sketch she was not human, but a creature. This is how her daughter sees her- bull-faced and miserable. All Delores's secrets and insecurities are exposed in the gaze of this child" (157). While Dolores' character emphasises the generational cycle of trauma, poverty, and exploitation, her younger daughter Thandi is altogether a different story.

Thandi, as a teenager who lives with the burden of her family's dreams, witnesses a world where she does not have a voice. She is denied the right to make any decisions or even to follow her passion. She is convinced by society that for a woman to be acceptable, her skin colour matters. The dirty politics of the society's expectations and norms forced her to choose skin lightening despite the consequences. The frequent reminder of being black affected her

self and individuality so much that she believed herself as socially disabled. To substantiate this inclination towards self-hatred, here are the intriguing words by Malcolm X:

We hated the African characteristics. We hated our hair. We hated our nose, the shape of our nose, and the shape of our lips, the color of our skin. Yes, we did. And it was you who taught us to hate ourselves simply by shrewdly maneuvering us into hating the land of our forefathers and the people on that continent. As long as we hated those people, we hated ourselves. As long as we hated what we thought they looked like, we hated what we actually looked like. “When you teach a man to hate his lips, the lips that God gave him, the shape of the nose that God gave him, the texture of the hair that God gave him, the color of the skin that God gave him, you’ve committed the worst crime that a race of people can commit. And this is the crime that you’ve committed. “Our color became a chain, a psychological chain. Our blood — African blood — became a psychological chain, a prison, because we were ashamed of it. We felt trapped because our skin was black. We felt trapped because we had African blood in our veins. (Malcom X 9)

This idea of self-hatred bears out the fact that the denial of god gifted features to blindly embrace the stereotyped beauty makes people devoid of their real identity. Thus, by trying to fit into the societal beauty standards, everything becomes a chain; a psychological, physical and social chain.

Along with these major characters, several other characters also manifest how the female body reacts to the societal norms determined by those in power. Verde, who is marked by isolation and resilience, has to face ostracism and hostility due to her homo sexual orientation. Simultaneously, Juliette has to change her identity and become a prostitute in order

to survive in society. Though she enters this immoral work with apprehension, her gradual procurement and reception among her fellow workers and clients encourage her to trade her body for money. Almost all the female characters have to compromise their possession of their own bodies at different points or throughout. While some have to incline towards the fate, others use it as a tool against domination.

Analysing the novel *Here Comes the Sun*, the element of body politics is reflected through different components such as family, tourism, colourism, sexuality, identity, etc. Such components work in the lives of the characters, mostly in a negative shade. To resist these social norms and escape from their struggles, each character has to take chances that could affect their family or their own dreams and passions. A completely happy life is a far-fetched dream for them. No alteration in their real self can alter their position in society. The very opinion of Margot states: “No matter what yuh do to yuhself, it not g’wan change a t’ing,” Margot says to Thandi. “Believe me, it won’t change yuh place in society or how they look at you” (184). Amidst all the chaos, tourism and its related consequences struck the people like an unexpected tornado. Though they are supported by the economy from tourism to a point, they are being severely damaged due to the adverse effects of the same.

Identity crisis with a particular reference to body politics encompasses different dimensions of society, including race, class, gender, sexuality, colour, etc. And these elements are based on society’s established norms and expectations, along with the inculcation of societal ideologies. The characters in *Here Comes the Sun* clearly represent the Jamaican islanders and their lives. Skin bleaching has flourished in Jamaica because they believe that having lighter or fairer skin is a symbol of being beautiful. Even young minds are being taught about the beauty standards that make them acceptable in society and peer groups. Making alterations to their genuine selves could help them gain a bit of confidence, but rather lead to

an identity crisis. In the novel, the characters are perplexed not only about their skin colour according to their race, but also about their sexuality. Though they are aware of their sexual orientation, they have to obscure it from society and their fellow beings. Such elements play a vital role in executing body politics in the novel.

People often say a family is not a choice, but God's gift. But what if this same gift turns into a curse? In *Here Comes the Sun*, the personal, familial, and societal pressures intersect in such a way that this God's gift becomes a burden instead of a comfort. The female bodies are controlled and commodified within the familial and societal structures in the name of economic gain as well as achieving goals. Margot, one of the pivotal characters, upholds the theme of body politics through her sacrifice of her body for her family. Her job in the hotel extends to a point where she sells sex to the premium customers in order to provide for her family and her sister's education. Thus, Margot's body becomes a site of economic transaction, and she herself has started seeing it as nothing other than a commodity. Though she started it as a means of survival, gradually her body became a tool that helped her to elevate in social status. Margot does not confine to the commodification and exploitation of the female body. She insisted that many other women work for her in Alphonso's resort by being their boss lady. The women who were denied at first have to give hands with their so-called boss lady as a reminder of their family stroked their heads. Money could overpower their helplessness in meeting both ends.

Thandi, Margot's younger sister, represents the next generation suffering under body politics. She is burdened with her family's pressure to excel academically and become a doctor. Her passion to become an artist vanishes into thin air under the weight of her family's dreams about her. Margot was an athlete once, but she had to give up her love for sports for her family:

Thandi delights in the sturdiness of Margot's calves, conjuring up memories of her running track at the small secondary school she attended. Margot made it to

girl's champs and could have gone further in track and field. But for some reason, she stopped training and fell off the path. When Thandi asked her why, Margot responded with a casual shrug. "It wasn't worth it" (39).

Destiny plays a role in the lives of marginalised people by fanning the flames. While her mind is disturbed by familial expectations, her body is tortured by societal expectations and beauty standards. The pressure instilled on Thandi amplified her dilemma about which path to choose. Her love for Charles could be an escape from all the burdens her family and society put on her. Such a form of resistance against the expectations becomes mandatory for her survival.

Dolores, mother of Thandi and Margot, fortifies body politics within her family by exerting pressure on her daughters for higher social mobility. The trauma resulting from her worst past experiences, like abuse, body shaming, poverty, and racism, made her stubborn and harsh to everyone around them. Thandi's indifference and Dolores's hatred make Margot's efforts end up in futile. Destiny, along with a cycle of traumas, made them victims of body politics exercised by a judgmental society. When Margot tried to save her family from poverty, she had to give up everything:

Thandi whom she clothed, sheltered, fed, gave every bit of herself to. With her body she shielded her sister from Dolores's wrath. Gave her an opportunity to get away. To be better than them so she wouldn't have to sacrifice anything. But instead of gratitude in Thandi's eyes, Margot sees the looming resentment. "You don't even know yuhself. My childhood was spent like a hundred dollar bill on you. Everything you needed was put on me. If yuh needed formula, I had to sleep wid yuh father to get it. If yuh cry fah hunger, I had to feed you. If yuh

wanted a special toy, I had to get down on my knees an' do more than play. I had to play wid yuh daddy too." (271)

But at the end, when Margot has achieved all the luxury, she does not possess a family of her own.

Tourism and its further consequences do their part by adding fuel to the fire on these poor people. The commodification of female bodies can be paralleled with the commodification of landscapes. When tourism aided the people of Montego Bay, it adversely affected them by digging up their roots. They are forced to leave their native place to bring in more development in the tourism sector. Thus, *Here Comes the Sun* portrays the two facets of the same issue.

Considering women characters, most of them depend on tourism for their survival and to make ends meet. Delores is running a shop that sells souvenirs and island products to the tourists. Though she has to bargain a lot with them, every penny she earns is so special for her. Her source of income to fulfil Thandi's education is obtained from tourism. But the same tourism has taken away the virginity of her elder daughter Margot when she was just fourteen. The manipulation of nature and its resources reflects the exploitation of human bodies for economic gain:

One by one they begin to knock down trees in the cove and along the river. They also take a chunk of the hill, cutting down the trees that cradle the limestone, which they chip away. Their big engines grind two-thousand-year-old tree trunks- trees the ancestors once hid behind, crouching in search of freedom. The workmen, imported from overseas, gather the fishing boats and load them on a truck. The men fold the earth in ways Thandi would have thought

impossible. Bits and pieces of rock scatter as trees are uprooted. When they collapse, the earth shakes. A huge silence follows. (231)

The economic inequality exacerbated by tourism affected people of Jamaica, despite their gender and age. Though Margot is a hotelier because of the flourishing of tourism, her very home is on the verge of destruction due to the same development. She enters a dilemma on where to stand or with whom to stand, whether with her fellow neighbours and be sincere to her people or to be with Alphonso and safeguard her job and aspirations.

When new resorts and hotel chains take over River bank, it mirrors how the place and people are being transformed physically and culturally as well. Displacement from their own place leads them to a deeper trauma, as they have no privileges to migrate and live a bountiful life. The natives are forced to adapt and cater to the needs of tourists and those in power, like Alphonso. The tourists manipulate the vulnerability and powerlessness of the indigenous people. The loss of nature and its resources gradually leads to the loss of culture, beliefs and cuisines as well. When Alphonso hires a cook who can satiate the taste buds of foreigners, he disregards the native cuisine and tastes.

The rich tourists perceive Jamaican women as just objects and treat them as sex dolls. They believe their bodies are to be relished and left behind. This kind of exploitation, which arises mainly from tourism, portrays the struggles of the locals. Along with the people, their place, culture and even their language are mutilated by this external influence. Amidst the chaos, Margot tries to attain a better quality of life by making use of her body and making decisions. Many a time, Alphonso becomes a puppet in Margot's hands, knowingly or unknowingly, where she plays a reversal of fate. Although she could do it due to her powerful mind, the rest of the characters still suffer when the novel ends.

Likewise, *Here Comes the Sun* also illustrates how colourism and society's expectation of beauty standards have a great impact on the lives and dreams of people, especially those who are underprivileged. While it affects social and financial mobility, it brings out the inferiority complex and leads to emotional trauma. The rigid beauty standard is a recurring theme in this novel that mirrors the body politics that exist in Jamaican society.

Throughout the novel, the readers witness a society that equates lighter skin with beauty and success. The prejudices on these matters in society seriously affect women, particularly those who are of a tender age. Once they get exposed to body shaming and neglect due to their skin colour and physical features, it can lead to lifelong trauma. Along with her past experiences of physical abuse, Delores had to undergo body shaming when she was eighteen. Her visit to Kingston for the first time and the humiliation she faced there changed her life and perspective. She never imagined in her remotest dreams that her visit to Kingston in search of a temporary job would make her a laughing stock in front of the Kingstonians. Though she was happy with her bright yellow dress with lace and puffed-up sleeves, the elite people laughed at her for her mediocre fashion sense, which did not suit her skin colour. The moment made her believe what her mother told her in the very morning: "If me was suh big an' black, me woulda neva mek scarecrow come catch me inna dat color. Yuh bettah hope di people inna Kingston nuh laugh yuh backside back ah country" (66). She felt like a veil had lifted from her eyes; her perspectives and confidence about her body had diminished forever.

The thoughts of beauty standards are being inculcated in the mind of Thandi, too. She is convinced by Miss. Ruby that "God nuh likes ugly" (15). This statement made her question her self-worth, and thereby, she pursued a fairer skin at any cost, even by trading her mental and physical health. Her view of the world is completely based on the societal expectations and beauty standards. Suffering all those discomforts resulting from the process of skin lightening,

Thandi is ready to embrace the change, expecting acceptance from her peer group and society. Margot is also affected by these notions of beauty and acceptance. She is portrayed as voluptuous and seductive in the novel. Even her customers and her boss, Alphonso, see her as a body to have intercourse with, but not to be in love with. Being a person who has tasted much more bitterness in life, she is used to such humiliations and uses her body as a tool to achieve anything she desires.

According to Judith Butler, “The body implies mortality, vulnerability, agency: the skin and the flesh expose us to the gaze of others but also to touch and to violence, and bodies put us at risk of becoming the agency and instrument of all these as well. (26) Women’s bodies and appearances are determined by colonial standards and the patriarchal society. The treatment of the female body according to its appearance is nothing but distressing. In order to fit in, they will have to adopt uncomfortable ways and means that have the potential to affect their mental as well as physical strength. Alongside these elements of body politics, a deep and complex exploration of sexuality and identity is thoughtfully portrayed by Nicole Dennis-Benn in her debut novel. The majority of the characters are forced to keep their sexuality and identity obscure due to rigid social norms and conditions. While Margot shows her powerful character throughout, at times, she fails due to her hidden sexuality, which she is unable to expose in a homophobic society. When she realises that her homosexual orientation could bring her the tag of a witch and can be a reason to be ostracised, she desires to move to a new place, leaving behind her roots: “She always wanted to leave River Bank anyway. With the new promotion, she can send Thandi to sixth form in Kingston and then to university. She can buy the house she has been dreaming about in Lagoons and convince Verdene to come and live with her as a housemate (168). Her longing to express her true self has been carved inside out many times, which has even strained her relationship with Verdene.

Thandi's search for self prompts her to try a physical encounter with Charles. Her identity crisis revolves around the complications arising from societal expectations and the beauty standards instilled in her mind. Along with the family pressure to follow an academic discipline that she is least interested in, Thandi is totally confused about living her own life. Through skin bleaching, she neither belongs to the black nor the fair one, though. Studying in a convent school standardised her patois, and thus she does not completely belong to her community. Societal pressures and external influences altered her real identity as a black Jamaican. Even Margot's dual sexuality creates a sexual identity crisis. It is evident that she is homosexual. But she has to undergo multiple sexual encounters with men, which creates confusion about her sexuality. She is unable to express her true self and her love for Verdene due to societal values. The author of the novel, *Here Comes the Sun*, could beautifully portray the difficulties and experiences of homosexuality authentically, as she has such an orientation. This real-life discovery aids in exploring true-life incidents of identity crisis and strained sexuality among homosexual people.

Though body politics is considered a developing area of study, it has existed in our society for ages. People were forced to normalise the atrocities and swallow it as such. In *Here Comes the Sun*, Nicole Dennis-Benn portrayed how the bodies of women, particularly Black Jamaican Women, are subjected to the social, economic, cultural and gender politics. The policies and the so-called values designed by those in power created the ideologies of beauty standards and gender normalcy. Anything or anyone that deviates from these societal norms becomes socially disabled and neglected. The trauma arising due to familial and societal pressures affects generations of people. It is said that colonialism is long gone, but the footprints set by it still exist in the form of racism and colourism. Such prejudices create an identity crisis in the people who are subjected to it. Through the portrayal of women like

Margot, Thandi and Delore, along with several other minor characters, Nicole Dennis-Benn voiced the voiceless screams of Black Jamaican women.

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